

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW - PAPER INDEX

Total Papers Retrieved: 428 **Date Range:** 2020-2026 **Databases:** Web of Science, Google Scholar, and PubMed

2026 (29 papers)

212. Public Health, Safety, and Environmental Risk Exposure and Corporate Fraud. - **Authors:** Liang, Yang - **Journal/Venue:** Risk analysis : an official publication of the Society for Risk Analysis - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1111/risa.70186

213. A new quest for green finance and ESG excellence: A new perspective on energy efficiency. - **Authors:** Cao, Zhou, Chen et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128497

230. Green transformation or greenwashing? Strategic options for competitiveness in corporate green activities. - **Authors:** Duan, Liu, Ren et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2026.128546

235. The weight of silent criteria: ESG score performance and investment attractiveness in sub-Saharan Africa. - **Authors:** Messie Pondie, Berriche, Laroutis - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128192

252. Environmental taxation, supply chain dynamics, and corporate ESG performance. - **Authors:** Wang, Huang, Taghizadeh-Hesary - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128304

256. Board gender diversity and emissions performance: Insights from panel regressions, machine learning, and explainable AI. - **Authors:** Shakil, Pollestad, Kyaw et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2026.128776

263. Supervisor bottom line mentality and its impact on employee outcomes: The mediating role of employee appraisals. - **Authors:** Naseer, Naqvi - **Journal/Venue:** PloS one - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1371/journal.pone.0338024

286. Increasing the environmental sustainability of operating rooms in Canada: an evidence-informed guideline for policy. - **Authors:** Goldman, Pearsall, Liu et al. - **Journal/Venue:** CMAJ : Canadian Medical Association journal = journal de

l'Association medicale canadienne - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article
- **DOI:** 10.1503/cmaj.251192

313. Corporate social responsibility and employee performance in China's manufacturing sector: Exploring the roles of altruistic values and organizational identification. - **Authors:** Fu, Ruangoon, Thavorn - **Journal/Venue:** PloS one - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1371/journal.pone.0339484

314. Staff awareness and engagement with the Green Plan: A cross-sectional survey of one of the largest NHS trusts in the UK. - **Authors:** Madan - **Journal/Venue:** Health policy (Amsterdam, Netherlands) - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.healthpol.2026.105576

316. Resilience capacity of aquaculture farmers in climate vulnerable areas of Bangladesh. - **Authors:** Hussain, Sabbir, Munmun et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2026.128768

318. The ESG Flow-Return Paradox: Green sentiment boosts inflows but lags in returns. - **Authors:** Gao, Perdana - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128385

328. Does regularity quality enhance sustainability performance? International evidence. - **Authors:** Zaman, Eskandari, Khan - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128387

334. Understanding how organizational socialization shapes organizational commitment: A qualitative study in the aviation industry. - **Authors:** Türk, Udum - **Journal/Venue:** Acta psychologica - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.106115

344. From conflict to collaboration: how local natural resource management conventions foster peacebuilding between farmers and herders in central Mali. - **Authors:** Ba, Affognon, Flintan - **Journal/Venue:** Disasters - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1111/disa.70043

388. Playing against the clock: The hidden costs of circadian disruption in the football ecosystem of performance, recovery and spectator engagement. - **Authors:** Bagci, Izmir Tunahan, Bademci - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of sports sciences - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1080/02640414.2026.2623568

391. Bridging the implementation gap: Challenges and opportunities for integrating whole genome sequencing in tuberculosis surveillance in low-resource settings. - **Authors:** Micheni, Wambua, Magutah et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Diagnostic

microbiology and infectious disease - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.diagmicrobio.2026.117282

393. Reforming schools into health promoting schools: perspective based on expert consensus from a European multistakeholder consultation. - **Authors:** Makris, Philippou, Vasileiou et al. - **Journal/Venue:** European journal of pediatrics - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s00431-025-06736-y

395. Generative Artificial Intelligence for Environmental Assessment: A New Paradigm for Sustainability Analysis. - **Authors:** Rahman, Raihan, Abudalfa - **Journal/Venue:** Environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s00267-026-02402-7

401. Global soybean trade dynamics: Drivers, impacts, and sustainability. - **Authors:** Peng, Zhang, Zhang et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Innovation (Cambridge (Mass.)) - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.xinn.2025.101124

402. Big data in healthcare and medicine revisited design and managerial challenges in the age of artificial intelligence. - **Authors:** Raghupathi, Raghupathi - **Journal/Venue:** Health information science and systems - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s13755-026-00433-2

406. Reimagining primary health care: a historical and contemporary scoping review of community-based primary health care models and innovations. - **Authors:** Acharya, Mishra, von Seidlein et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Preventive medicine reports - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.pmedr.2026.103390

410. Emerging trends in genome editing of wild animals. - **Authors:** Blix, Myhr - **Journal/Venue:** Transgenic research - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s11248-026-00483-y

411. Conservation and environmental management reimagined: Toward anti-oppressive futures. - **Authors:** German, Abrams, Struthers et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1073/pnas.2414948123

412. Financial Reasoning in Radiology: Interpreting Risk, Value, and Capital Allocation for Resilient and High-Value Imaging Services. - **Authors:** Kamran, Patlas - **Journal/Venue:** Canadian Association of Radiologists journal = Journal l'Association canadienne des radiologistes - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1177/08465371261419016

414. Intertwined threats of nationalized nature and privatized ecological research for global biodiversity conservation. - **Authors:** Haubrock, Everts, Kouba et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Conservation biology : the journal of the Society for Conservation Biology - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1111/cobi.70228

415. From roads to oceans: Pollution pathways of end-of-life tires in coastal and marine environments. - **Authors:** Rangel-Buitrago, Neal, Galgani - **Journal/Venue:** Marine pollution bulletin - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2026.119355

416. Sustainable PFAS Removal from Electronics Wastewater through a Cost-Health Trade-Off Framework. - **Authors:** Wang, You - **Journal/Venue:** Environmental science & technology - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1021/acs.est.5c15514

426. Examining the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational culture and organizational change perception in a hospital setting: a structural equation modeling approach. - **Authors:** Orhan, Akbulut - **Journal/Venue:** Leadership in health services (Bradford, England) - **Publication Date:** 2026 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/LHS-10-2025-0167

2025 (95 papers)

4. Future-proofing the workforce: A fuzzy AHP-MARCOS model for evaluating green and digital reskilling in the ESG era. - **Authors:** Ragazou, Zournatzidou, Sklavos et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128146

8. Advancing Healthcare Sustainability Through Integrated Triple Bottom Line Implementation: A Comprehensive Framework for Economic Prosperity, Environmental Quality, and Social Equity - **Authors:** Amin A. Sadabadi - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-12 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.31235/osf.io/h2na6_v1

9. People, Planet, and Profits - HR's Role in Fostering Innovative Sustainable Development in Management - **Authors:** P.K. Anjani, G. Padmanaban, Prakriti Koirala - **Journal/Venue:** Social Science Research Network - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Repository - **DOI:** 10.2139/ssrn.5075867

10. Sostenibilidad Corporativa y ESG (Environmental, Social And Governance) - **Authors:** Diana Priscila Ortega Romero, Fabian Mauricio Tello Velastegui, Vinicio Fabian Ortega Romero - **Journal/Venue:** Dominio de las Ciencias - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.23857/dc.v11i1.4229

13. A Literature Review of Environmental, Social, and Governance - **Authors:** Linxuan Wang, Sait Abdullah, Jason See Toh et al. - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-29 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.70088/h6h74e32

15. Sustainability in human resource management: a framework for ecological and inclusive excellence - **Authors:** Sapna Damor, Barkha Agrawal - **Journal/Venue:** GLOBAL JOURNAL FOR RESEARCH ANALYSIS - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-15 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36106/gjra/2606636

18. The Ethical Edge: Modern Business Management Meets Environmental and Social Responsibility - **Authors:** Phanutat Sawadthaworn, Thanyachanok Pawala, Paripon Jumroenpat et al. - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of Sociologies and Anthropologies Science reviews - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-27 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.60027/ijsasr.2025.7580

21. From Shareholder Value to Stakeholder Impact: Integrating ESG Considerations into Financial Decisions - **Authors:** John A. Oyetade, Olomiyete Igbalawole, Samuel F. Johnson-Rokosu - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of research and innovation in social science - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.47772/ijriss.2025.9020021

22. Sustentabilidade empresarial como vantagem competitiva: Práticas ESG na administração de negócios do século XXI - **Authors:** Antonio Esmerahdson de Pinho da Silva, Edmilson Monteiro de Souza, Rubens Savaris Leal et al. - **Journal/Venue:** IOSR Journal of Business and Management - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.9790/487x-2706081838

24. The evolving role of sustainable human resource management - **Authors:** Thanuja Vickneswaran - **Journal/Venue:** Strategic Hr Review - **Publication Date:** 2025-03-25 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/shr-02-2025-0018

25. The Integration of Sustainability Practices in Global Human Resource Management Strategy - **Authors:** Smriti Tandon, Navin Kumar, Pawan Kumar - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-02 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3373-1005-3.ch024

37. Corporate Social Responsibility: Foundations, Practices, and Implications for Sustainable Development - **Authors:** Anna Neya Kazanskaia - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.64357/neya-gjnps-csr-lg-eth-ss-01

42. Strategic and sustainable human resource management: Twin weapon for achieving competitive advantage in organization - **Authors:** William Ben Gunawan, L Tsurcan Mikhail - **Journal/Venue:** Priviet Social Sciences Journal - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-23 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.55942/pssj.v5i6.401

48. Corporate Sustainability, ESG, and the Triple Bottom Line: A Review of Key Challenges - **Authors:** Tilak Ch Das, Prabin Kumar Bora, J. P. Das - **Journal/Venue:** International Review of Management and Marketing - **Publication Date:** 2025-08-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.32479/irmm.19768

53. A Triple Bottom Line Performance Measurement Model for The Sustainability of Post-Mining Landscapes of Indonesia - **Authors:** Justan Riduan Siahaan, Gagaring Pagalung, Eymal Bahsar Demmallino et al. - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-06 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.20944/preprints202505.0126.v1

- 59.** Integrating Sustainability Principles Into Human Resource Management - **Authors:** K. Keerthi Jain - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-06 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3373-4546-8.ch002
- 70.** Triple Bottom-Line: A Critical Review and Need for Strategic Renewal - **Authors:** Asif Ali Bhatti, Junaid Rehman, M Shamsi et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Pakistan Business Review - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-15 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.22555/pbr.v27i1.1368
- 74.** Organizational Sustainability Management Governance - **Authors:** José G. Vargas-Hernández, Francisco J. González-Ávila, Omar C. Vargas-González et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in logistics, operations, and management science book series - **Publication Date:** 2025-02-14 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3373-2106-6.ch001
- 83.** Csr, sustainability, governance, and accountability: their position in the body of knowledge - **Authors:** Hasan Fauzi - **Journal/Venue:** International Journal of Contemporary Accounting - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-29 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.25105/v7i1.22868
- 90.** Integrating Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Principles into Financial Planning for Sustainable Corporate Growth - **Authors:** Oludolapo Olutosin Amole, Michael Emedo - **Journal/Venue:** Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.9734/ajarr/2025/v19i1861
- 100.** Green Human Resource Management (GHRM): A Strategic Approach to Sustainability and Employee Engagement - **Authors:** Dahlia Abdulhussein Ahmed, Mohd Azli Salim, Mustafa Ali Ibrahim - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of transformation in business management - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.37648/ijtbn.v15i03.003
- 104.** Environmental Sustainability: The Case of a Multi-Business Packaging Organisation in South Africa - **Authors:** Manduth Ramchander, Manikam Michael Nadar - **Journal/Venue:** Brics journal - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-28 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36615/1dyavh40
- 105.** Environmental management system certification and corporate ESG greenwashing - **Authors:** Zhonghua Cheng, Xueqin Yan - **Journal/Venue:** Energy Economics - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.eneco.2025.108800
- 110.** Sustainable Workplaces and Employee Well-Being: A Systematic Review of ESG-Linked Physical Activity Programs. - **Authors:** Chen, Fang - **Journal/Venue:** Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland) - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/healthcare13233146

- 120.** Perspectives on Sustainable Business Strategy - **Authors:** Haonan Zhang - **Journal/Venue:** Frontiers in business, economics and management - **Publication Date:** 2025-02-21 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54097/pjgv9479
- 122.** Perspectives on Sustainable Business Strategy - **Authors:** Haonan Zhang - **Journal/Venue:** Academic journal of science and technology - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-20 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54097/1s4x5e82
- 132.** Integrating ESG Principles into Corporate Strategic Management: Implementation Pathways and Performance Evaluation Systems - **Authors:** Li Li - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-20 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.64229/51qp6898
- 133.** Integrating Sustainability into Corporate Strategy: Challenges and Best Practices - **Authors:** Rajiv N. Thakkar - **Journal/Venue:** Deleted Journal - **Publication Date:** 2025-03-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.47392/irjaem.2025.0112
- 134.** Corporate ESG Performance: Research Review and Prospects - **Authors:** Menglu Ni - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2025-08-13 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54254/2754-1169/2025.lh25901
- 136.** Sustainability and Corporate Governance: The Impact of ESG Policies on Business Strategy - **Authors:** Yuxin Wang - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2025-04-24 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54254/2754-1169/2025.ab22448
- 137.** The role of esg in driving corporate sustainability practices in the context of globalization challenges - **Authors:** Rani Rachmawati, Sri Sutrismi, Sawal Sartono - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-09-24 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.32424/icsema.v1i1.449
- 144.** The Global Landscape of ESG Guidelines and Standards: Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible Investment, and ESG Compliance - **Authors:** Corinna Irina Ketterling - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-23 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.31219/osf.io/47efm_v3
- 148.** The Global Landscape of ESG Guidelines and Standards: Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible Investment, and ESG Compliance - **Authors:** Corinna Irina Ketterling - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-25 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.31219/osf.io/47efm_v4
- 151.** Examining the role of environmental social and governance metrics in financial reporting and investment decision-making during corporate mergers - **Authors:** Olajide Alex Ajide, Aramide Ajayi, Emmanuel Egyam et al. - **Journal/Venue:** World Journal Of Advanced Research and Reviews - **Publication Date:** 2025-09-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.30574/wjarr.2025.27.3.3255

- 152.** Integrating ESG Criteria in Corporate Strategies: Determinants and Implications for Performance - **Authors:** Houda Alhoussari - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of ecohumanism - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-12 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.62754/joe.v3i8.5791
- 153.** The Global Landscape of ESG Guidelines and Standards: Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible Investment, and ESG Compliance - **Authors:** Corinna Irina Ketterling - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-18 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.31219/osf.io/47efm
- 159.** Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Integration in Bangladesh: Revealing the Role of Corporate Governance Nexus - **Authors:** Imran Khan, Anup Kumar Saha, Md. Anisul Islam Sajib et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of financial markets and governance - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54728/jfmg.202409.00081
- 162.** The greenwashing trap under decarbonisation pressure: How carbon risk drives corporate ESG greenwashing?-Empirical evidence from China's capital markets. - **Authors:** Dai, Bao, Wang - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128193
- 166.** Green Human Resource Management for Resource Sustainability - **Authors:** S. Shalini, R. Sivakumar - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in computational intelligence and robotics book series - **Publication Date:** 2025-02-28 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-9375-8.ch005
- 167.** A Study on HR Sustainability in an IT Company in Chennai - **Authors:** P. V., T S Sindhuja - **Journal/Venue:** International Scientific Journal of Engineering and Management - **Publication Date:** 2025-09-02 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.55041/isjem.eseh037
- 176.** Climate commitment: The impact of ESG, green innovation, and environmental governance on Canadian and U.S. companies. - **Authors:** Ben Mehrez, Farhat, Ajina - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of environmental management - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.128108
- 178.** Female leadership and ESG rating disagreement: Evidence from China. - **Authors:** Liao, Chen - **Journal/Venue:** Scientific reports - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1038/s41598-025-30948-9
- 180.** A double-edged sword: materiality classifications of sustainability topics. - **Authors:** Göttsche, Griffin, Habermann et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Review of accounting studies - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s11142-025-09908-1
- 183.** Green Finance and Corporate ESG Practices: A Dual-Driving Mechanism for Promoting Sustainable Development - **Authors:** Jiaxin Zhang - **Journal/Venue:**

Frontiers in business, economics and management - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-21
- **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54097/hbyz4678

192. Examining the Relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility Practices and Sustainability in Organizations Within the Framework of Stakeholder Theory - **Authors:** Gülşen Yurdakul - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36880/c17.03054

199. Strategic decoupling through legitimacy: the sustainability-innovation gap in the food processing sector and its health implications. - **Authors:** Yucel - **Journal/Venue:** Globalization and health - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1186/s12992-025-01166-9

203. “It’s Not an Add-On; It’s One of Our Big Bets”: Shifting Discourse From CSR to ESG - **Authors:** Rose Helens-Hart, Jenna Haugen, Lauren Reuss - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of business communication - **Publication Date:** 2025-09-25 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1177/23294884251374621

206. Environmental, social, and governance (esg) standards in search of a new paradigm of responsibility - **Authors:** Oksana Hutsalenko, Галина Подольн - **Journal/Venue:** Visnik Kiivs'kogo nacional'nogo univrsitetu imeni Tarasa Ševčenka - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.17721/2523-4064.2025/12-10/23

207. In-depth Analysis and Prospect of Factors Influencing Corporate ESG Performance - **Authors:** Xichen Wang - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-10 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54254/2754-1169/2025.20075

210. Optimizing Sustainability: Aligning Environmental Management Systems with Green Supply Chain Management - **Authors:** Martin O. Agbili, Christian C Odoh - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of research and scientific innovation - **Publication Date:** 2025-04-27 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.51244/ijrsi.2025.12040006

218. O environmental, social and governance-esg como vetor jurídico de transformação empresarial: da responsabilidade social à accountability regulatória - **Authors:** Anna Christine Silveira Sampaio Carloto - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-04-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.63391/0e05d1

221. How Sustainability Is Core for Human Resource Management? A Conceptual Frame Work - **Authors:** Ashok Sengupta - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of informatics education and research - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-24 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.52783/jier.v5i2.3029

227. Sustainability Strategies: Driving Profitability Through Environmental Responsibility - **Authors:** Parul Gupta - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of information technology and management - **Publication Date:** 2025-02-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.29070/wthx5291

- 229.** Do ESG Frameworks Capture Corporate Health Impacts? An Analysis of the Food and Beverage Industry. - **Authors:** Burgess, Chen, Kim et al. - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of environmental research and public health - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/ijerph23010030
- 243.** GREEN HRM & ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY: A SYNERGY OF INNOVATIONS - **Authors:** Khushboo Sharma, Pallavi Mehta - **Journal/Venue:** PARIPEX INDIAN JOURNAL OF RESEARCH - **Publication Date:** 2025-07-15 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36106/paripex/6805748
- 271.** The Role of Environmental Management Systems (EMS) in Driving Organizational Development and Environmental Sustainability - **Authors:** Ghassan Mazraani, Mario Tucci - **Journal/Venue:** American Journal of Environment and Climate - **Publication Date:** 2025-01-25 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54536/ajec.v4i1.3748
- 281.** The Global Landscape of ESG Guidelines and Standards: Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible Investment, and ESG Compliance - **Authors:** Corinna Irina Ketterling - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-19 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.31219/osf.io/47efm_v1
- 285.** Internal security vs. external options: a goal-shielding explanation of how employability differentially shapes unethical pro-organizational behavior. - **Authors:** Niu, Liu, Niu - **Journal/Venue:** Frontiers in psychology - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1605697
- 288.** The Dark Side of Bottom-Line Thinking: How Supervisors' Bottom-Line Mentality Stifles Employee Voice and Innovative Work Behavior? - **Authors:** Imran Hameed - **Journal/Venue:** Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2025-06-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.64534/comm.2025.006
- 297.** ESG in Practice - **Authors:** Tímea Veres, Júlia Tobak, Georgina Nagy - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in environmental engineering and green technologies book series - **Publication Date:** 2025-03-28 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3373-0045-0.ch012
- 306.** Green HRM Bridging Sustainability and Workforce Management - **Authors:** Mohi Ud Din, Muhammad Faizan Khan - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2025-05-02 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3373-0139-6.ch003
- 307.** Impact of Ethical Leadership on Organizational Performance and Employee Engagement: A Comprehensive Review - **Authors:** Rachna Paliwal, Jitu Nagda - **Journal/Venue:** International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research - **Publication Date:** 2025-09-17 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36948/ijfmr.2025.v07i05.55839
- 308.** A twenty-two-year journey of sustainable human resource management research: bibliometric analysis - **Authors:** Md. Nazmus Sakib, Md Salah Uddin,

Towhida Akter Kona et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Future Business Journal - **Publication Date:** 2025-08-05 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1186/s43093-025-00608-5

310. Integrating business management strategies to address HIV stigma and support employees in diverse workplaces. - **Authors:** Zhou, Hu - **Journal/Venue:** AIDS reviews - **Publication Date:** 2025 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.24875/AIDSRev.25000009

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- 145.** Governance of Organizational Sustainability Management - **Authors:** José G. Vargas-Hernández, Francisco J. González Ávila, Omar C. Vargas-González - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in business strategy and competitive advantage book series - **Publication Date:** 2024-12-27 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-8337-7.ch014
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- 161.** ESG controversies, corporate governance, and the market for corporate control - **Authors:** Sirimon Treepongkaruna, Khine S. Kyaw, Pornsit Jiraporn - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2024-04-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1080/20430795.2024.2334253
- 165.** Unifying Green HRM With Sustainable Development Goals - **Authors:** Himani Oberai, Ila Mehrotra Anand - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in human resources management and organizational development book series - **Publication Date:** 2024-11-29 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-6617-2.ch011
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al. - **Journal/Venue:** Practice, progress, and proficiency in sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2024-11-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-6522-9.ch008

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292. How and when supervisor bottom-line mentality affects employees' voluntary workplace green behaviors: A goal-shielding perspective - **Authors:** Junwei Zhang, Muhammad Naseer Akhtar, Yajun Zhang et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management - **Publication Date:** 2024-06-02 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1002/csr.2877

295. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Sustainability Through Corporate Social Responsibility - **Authors:** Jose John, I. S. Smiju, Kiran Thampi et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in logistics, operations, and management science book series - **Publication Date:** 2024-08-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-3880-3.ch002

298. Green HRM Practices - **Authors:** Aarzo Pilania - **Journal/Venue:** Indian Scientific Journal Of Research In Engineering And Management - **Publication Date:** 2024-05-09 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.55041/ijsrem33488

- 320.** Supervisor bottom-line mentality and employee workplace well-being: a multiple mediation model - **Authors:** Linyi Guo, Jing Du, Juncheng Zhang - **Journal/Venue:** Baltic Journal of Management - **Publication Date:** 2024-04-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/bjm-11-2023-0467
- 322.** When competitive rewards create obsessions with bottom-line outcomes: A social interdependence theory perspective of the mediating role of bottom-line mentality - **Authors:** Mary B. Mawritz, Rebecca L. Greenbaum, Yingli Deng et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of Organizational Behavior - **Publication Date:** 2024-04-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1002/job.2791
- 332.** The moderating role of sales managers' political skill in lessening the impact of bottom-line mentality on emotional exhaustion of salespeople - **Authors:** Arti Pandey, Peerayuth Charoensukmongkol - **Journal/Venue:** Management Research Review - **Publication Date:** 2024-12-28 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/mrr-03-2024-0186
- 333.** Motivate or suppress: The dual effects of leader bottom-line mentality on employee innovation behavior - **Authors:** Shiwen Luo, David Yoon Kin Tong - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2024-11-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5283142/v1
- 338.** How leader bottom-line mentality impedes employee innovative behavior: a Pygmalion effect perspective - **Authors:** Tingxi Wang, Boming Yu, M. Liu et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Leadership & Organization Development Journal - **Publication Date:** 2024-09-11 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/lodj-03-2024-0167
- 342.** The effect of organizational ethics on increasing the performance of workers in small and medium-sized enterprises - **Authors:** Osman Sejfijaj, Hekuran Sabedini, Alberta Tahiri et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Nurture - **Publication Date:** 2024-06-12 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.55951/nurture.v18i3.749
- 345.** Work for them or myself: a motivational approach to study the influences of supervisor bottom-line mentality on employee exhaustion - **Authors:** Lu (Lucy) Xing, Mengxi Yang - **Journal/Venue:** European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology - **Publication Date:** 2024-02-14 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1080/1359432x.2024.2314931
- 347.** Research Trend in the Development of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) - **Authors:** Wu Zhao - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2024-11-29 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54254/2754-1169/2024.17815
- 348.** All work and no play makes Jack a dull boy: How and when supervisor bottom-line mentality hinders employee creativity - **Authors:** Xiumei Zhu, Mengxi Yang, Yuanmei Qu et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Applied Psychology - **Publication Date:** 2024-10-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1111/apps.12578

357. Improving work ethics and organizational citizenship behavior through positive cognitive and affective attitude toward work - **Authors:** Marlene T Nicolas - **Journal/Venue:** Divine word international journal of management and humanities - **Publication Date:** 2024-06-09 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.62025/dwijmh.v3i2.80

374. Workplace Ethics and Its Effects on Banking Sector Employees - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2024-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.52783/jier.v4i2.610

380. Greening the Corporate Landscape: the Role of CSR in Environmental Sustainability - **Authors:** Aniket Pathania -, Monika Rastogi - - **Journal/Venue:** International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research - **Publication Date:** 2024-06-13 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i03.22639

385. Oh the Anxiety! The Anxiety of Supervisor Bottom-Line Mentality and Mitigating Effects of Ethical Leadership - **Authors:** Marie S. Mitchell, Andrea L. Hetrick, Mary B. Mawritz et al. - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2024-09-01 - **Type:** Repository - **DOI:** 10.17615/7pf7-8h56

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1. Does the Environmental Management System Predict TBL Performance of Manufacturers? The Role of Green HRM Practices and OCBE as Serial Mediators - **Authors:** Guiling Yue, Ha Wei, Noor Ullah Khan et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15032436

3. Impact of green HRM practices on sustainable performance: mediating role of green innovation, green culture, and green employees' behavior - **Authors:** Muhammad Asim Shahzad, Du Jianguo, Muhammad Junaid - **Journal/Venue:** Environmental Science and Pollution Research - **Publication Date:** 2023-07-12 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s11356-023-28498-6

14. Impact of tripple bottom line assessment on sustainability of organization - **Authors:** Santosh Kumar Nc, Dr. K. Nirmala - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of research in management - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.33545/26648792.2023.v5.i2a.85

20. Imperatives, Benefits, and Initiatives of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM): A Systematic Literature Review - **Authors:** Fatimah Mohamed Mahdy, Mohammad Alqahtani, Faiz Binzafrah - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-09 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15064866

23. Environmental Management Accounting System Adoption and Sustainability Performance: Triple Bottom Line Approach - **Authors:** Nirman Noor, Afiqi Mat, Tuan Zainun et al. - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.24191/mar.v22i01-10

28. Corporate social responsibility oriented boards and triple bottom line performance: A meta-analytic study - **Authors:** Eugenio Zubeltzu-Jaka, Igor Alvarez-Etxeberria, Maider Aldaz-Odrizola - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-11-27 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1002/bsd2.320

31. Green Human Resource Management and Organizational Sustainability: A Systematic Literature Review and Bibliometric Analysis - **Authors:** Sania Khan, Shaha Faisal - **Journal/Venue:** International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-30 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.18280/ijstdp.180430

36. Sustainable of HRM System and Strategies for Corporate Sustainability - **Authors:** Touhidur Rahman Sajib, Md Jahidul Islam, Maniyarsi Gowindasamy - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-12-15 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.59857/ijabs.1470

38. Driving Social and Environmental Impact - **Authors:** Filiz Mızrak - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in business strategy and competitive advantage book series - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-29 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-0458-7.ch015

46. Does ESG Performance Affect Financial Performance? Evidence from Indonesia - **Authors:** Azharn Nafis Ihsani, Sulaeman Rahman Nidar, Meinanda Kurniawan - **Journal/Venue:** Wiga: Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu Ekonomi - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.30741/wiga.v13i1.968

52. Promoting Strategic Management Systems for Sustainable Business Models - **Authors:** Chukwuemeka Ugboma Azinge - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in business strategy and competitive advantage book series - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-29 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-0458-7.ch009

55. EESG Organizational Sustainability Management - **Authors:** Zara Cooper - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainable development goals series - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/978-3-031-36907-0_7

56. Fostering Sustainability Through the Integration of Green Human Resource Management and Change Management - **Authors:** Mary Viterouli, Dimitrios Belias, Αθανάσιος Κουστέλιος et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in human resources management and organizational development book series - **Publication Date:** 2023-10-09 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-0235-4.ch011

58. controversies about the relevance os esg from the perspective of value creation in the stakeholders capitalismo model - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** RISUS - Revista de Inovação e Sustentabilidade - **Publication Date:** 2023-05-30 - **Type:** article - **DOI:** 10.23925/2179-3565.2023v14i2p50-66

73. Examining the Impact of Environmental, Social and Governance Scores on Financial Performance of Listed Companies on the German Stock Exchange (XETRA) - **Authors:** Jacob Azaare, Zhao Wu, Ping Li et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Science journal of

business and management - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-18 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.11648/j.sjbm.20231102.12

75. Tata Kelola Perusahaan dan Keberlanjutan: Kinerja Triple Bottom Line - **Authors:** Eka Murtiasri, Prianka Ratri Nastiti, M.Pd . Iyus Akhmad Haris - **Journal/Venue:** Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis dan Ekonomi Kreatif - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-19 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.26877/jibeka.v2i2.197

81. Antecedents, outcomes, and boundaries of green human resource management: a literature review - **Authors:** Lydia Murillo-Ramos, Irene Huertas-Valdivia, Fernando E. García-Muiña - **Journal/Venue:** Rae-revista De Administracao De Empresas - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1590/s0034-759020230401

88. Green Human Resource Practices and Organizational Performance at Saudi Arabia - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** Al-Mağallah Al-‘ilmiyyah Lil-Iqtisād Wal Tiğārah (Print) - **Publication Date:** 2023-06-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.21608/jsec.2023.305226

91. The reality of the dimensions of sustainability in the business environment of micro and small companies of the Amazon portal that used the resource of the constitutional fund for Financing of the North – FNO - **Authors:** José Arilson de Souza, Raimundo Nonato Rodrigues - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-22 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.56238/uniknowindevolp-091

94. Triple bottom line, sustainability, and economic development: What binds them together? A bibliometric approach - **Authors:** Elisabete C Nogueira, Sofia Gomes, João Correia Lopes - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-15 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15086706

102. Does ESG Impact Firms' Sustainability Performance? The Mediating Effect of Innovation Performance - **Authors:** Md. Harun Ur Rashid, Shah Asadullah Mohd. Zobair, Farid Ahammad Sobhani et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15065586

106. Green HRM practices enhancing environmental performance through the mediating effect of commitment - **Authors:** Preeti Sharma - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of financial management and economics - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.33545/26179210.2023.v6.i1.173

107. Green Human Resource Management—A Synthesis - **Authors:** Shaha Faisal - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-26 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15032259

109. Strategic CSR: Framework for Sustainability through Management Systems Standards - Implementing and Disclosing Sustainable Development Goals and Results - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-06-14 - **Type:** Posted Content - **DOI:** 10.20944/preprints202306.1030.v1

116. The Role of Triple Bottom Line Reporting in Promoting Corporate Sustainability and Stakeholder Engagement - **Authors:** Fajar Mushtaq, Hannah Hameed, Arjun Baisla - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.48001/978-81-966500-9-4_17

125. The effect of GHRM on the sustainable performance of private companies in Qatar - **Authors:** Mohamad A. S Alenzi, Amar Hisham Jaaffar, Mohammad Khudari - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of management and sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-05-22 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.18488/11.v12i3.3376

127. Level of disclosure in sustainability reports in accordance with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) - **Authors:** A. Di Domenico - **Journal/Venue:** Revista Ambiente Contábil - **Publication Date:** 2023-07-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.21680/2176-9036.2023v15n2id33068

139. Avaliação de práticas ESG em bancos listados na [B]³ - **Authors:** Égon José Mateus Celestino, Mércia de Lima Pereira, Renata Paes de Barros Câmara - **Journal/Venue:** Revista Catarinense da Ciência Contábil - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.16930/2237-7662202333801

140. A Sustainable Development Evaluation Framework for Chinese Electricity Enterprises Based on SDG and ESG Coupling - **Authors:** Chaofeng Shao, Shuqi Xin, Zhirui Lu - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-06-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15118960

146. Avaliação de práticas ESG em bancos listados na [B]³ - **Authors:** Égon José Mateus Celestino, Mércia de Lima Pereira, Renata Paes de Barros Câmara - **Journal/Venue:** Revista Catarinense da Ciência Contábil - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.16930/2237-766220233380

160. Public governance, corporate governance and excessive ESG - **Authors:** Cemil Kuzey, Habiba Al-Shaer, Abdullah S. Karaman et al. - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-06-13 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/cg-01-2023-0028

163. Green Human Resource Management: A Comprehensive Analysis of Practices, Impacts, and Future Directions - **Authors:** Dyah Palupiningtyas, Sri Mulyani Wahono - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-12-31 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.56910/ictmt.v1i1.6

164. Tech-Enabled Sustainable HR Strategies: Fostering Green Practices - **Authors:** Rachna Bansal Jora, Prabhat Mittal, S.L. Kaushal - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-17 - **Type:** Proceedings Article - **DOI:** 10.1109/ICACCS57279.2023.10113050

177. An integrated MCDM framework for evaluating the environmental, social, and governance (ESG) sustainable business performance - **Authors:** Kerui Yu, Qun Wu,

Xiaoqing Chen et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Annals of Operations Research - **Publication Date:** 2023-10-10 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s10479-023-05616-8

186. Institutional pressures for sustainability: a triple bottom line approach - **Authors:** Susana Pasamar, Maria del Mar Bornay-Barrachina, Rafael Morales-Sánchez - **Journal/Venue:** European journal of management and business economics - **Publication Date:** 2023-12-26 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/ejmbe-07-2022-0241

187. The influence of external stakeholders on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) reporting: Toward a conceptual framework for ESG disclosure - **Authors:** Boon Heng Teh, Siow-Hooi Tan - **Journal/Venue:** Форсайт - **Publication Date:** 2023-06-25 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.17323/2500-2597.2023.2.9.20

193. Nível de disclosure nos relatórios de sustentabilidade em conformidade com o Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** Revista Ambiente Contábil - **Publication Date:** 2023-07-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.21680/2176-9036.2023v15n2id28710

215. Do Sustainability Activities Affect the Financial Performance of Banks? The Case of Indonesian Banks - **Authors:** Herenia Gutiérrez-Ponce, Sigit Arie Wibowo - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainability - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-19 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3390/su15086892

223. Concept of sustainable human resources management - **Authors:** Gulzhanat Tayauova - **Journal/Venue:** "Türan" universitetin habarsysy - **Publication Date:** 2023-07-05 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.46914/1562-2959-2023-1-2-272-284

225. Analysis of the World's Largest Eco-Funds: How Sustainable are Eco-Funds and are Their Choice of Holdings Influenced by Effects Other than the Level of Environmental Sustainability? - **Authors:** Matthew Malinsky - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.32920/24076512

226. The Importance of Triple Bottom Line Based Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability in the Modern Era - **Authors:** Yulisna Bunga - **Journal/Venue:** Social Science Research Network - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Repository - **DOI:** 10.2139/ssrn.4517342

242. Designing Ad Hoc Impact Monitoring Systems - **Authors:** Antonia Caro-González - **Journal/Venue:** SpringerBriefs in business - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-16 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.1007/978-3-031-43132-6_6

265. Applying the Triple Bottom Line for Corporate Sustainability Toward Zero Environmental, Social, and Economic Footprints in Corporate Practice - **Authors:** Emad Rahim - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in human and social aspects of technology book series - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-29 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-1630-6.ch009

267. Application and Analysis for Sustainability Strategy Development - **Authors:** Emad Rahim - **Journal/Venue:** Advances in business strategy and competitive advantage book series - **Publication Date:** 2023-10-16 - **Type:** Book Chapter - **DOI:** 10.4018/979-8-3693-1634-4.ch002

272. The construct of bottom-line mentality: Where we've been and where we're going - **Authors:** Rebecca L. Greenbaum, Mary B. Mawritz, Nazifa N. Zaman - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of Management - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-06 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1177/01492063231153135

274. Leveraging Value Creation Toward Business Models for Sustainability - **Authors:** M. Cabrita - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-10-09 - **Type:** Proceedings Article - **DOI:** 10.1109/icte58739.2023.10488582

280. A critical analysis on the triple bottom line of sustainable manufacturing: key findings and implications - **Authors:** W. S. Yip, Hongting Zhou, Suet To - **Journal/Venue:** Environmental Science and Pollution Research - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-12 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s11356-022-25122-x

283. Approaches to Managing Sustainability - **Authors:** Larissa Bilar - **Journal/Venue:** Sustainable development goals series - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/978-3-031-36907-0_6

284. A review of environmental, social and governance (ESG) regulatory frameworks: Their implications on Malaysia - **Authors:** Kuok Ho Daniel Tang - **Journal/Venue:** Tropical Aquatic and Soil Pollution - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-09 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.53623/tasp.v3i2.282

289. The Spillover Effect of Supervisor Bottom Line Mentality for Family Area: A Multipath Test - **Authors:** Shuwei Zong, Geng Li, Mingwei Liu - **Journal/Venue:** Proceedings - Academy of Management - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.5465/amproc.2023.17575abstract

296. The Impact of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) on Corporate Value Enhancement - **Authors:** Lanxi Zhang - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of education, humanities and social sciences - **Publication Date:** 2023-12-31 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54097/4mvdkn40

299. Sustainability of the society through green human resources management practices - **Authors:** YILKES DANLADI NSON - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-31 - **Type:** Preprint - **DOI:** 10.14293/pr2199.000332.v1

300. Sustainability-Centric Green Human Resource Management: An Imperative for the Contemporary Era - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** Annals of Human and Social Sciences - **Publication Date:** 2023-12-31 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.35484/ahss.2023(4-iv)18

301. Tech-Enabled Sustainable HR Strategies: Fostering Green Practices - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-17 - **Type:** Proceedings Article - **DOI:** 10.1109/icacccs57279.2023.10113050

302. Green Human Resources Management and its Relationship to Green Marketing Among the Employees of the University of Baghdad: Field Research at the University of Baghdad, College of Administration and Economics - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** International journal of research in social sciences and humanities - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.37648/ijrssh.v13i02.065

337. Bottom-line mentality and abusive supervisory behaviour in MSMEs: how do they affect employee outcomes? - **Authors:** Charles Hanu, Albert Tchev Agbenyegah, Gifty Kumadey et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of entrepreneurship in emerging economies - **Publication Date:** 2023-05-18 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/jeeee-07-2022-0215

353. Reject bias: A dialectical perspective on the relationship between bottom-line mentality and unethical pro-organizational behaviour - **Authors:** Guiqing Zhang, Shenbei Zhou, Yibin Li et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Asian Journal of Social Psychology - **Publication Date:** 2023-10-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1111/ajsp.12587

354. Oh the Anxiety! The Anxiety of Supervisor Bottom-Line Mentality and Mitigating Effects of Ethical Leadership - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of Management (Oluvil) - **Publication Date:** 2023-09-08 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1177/01492063231196553

363. Job Stress can be a Great Hurdle in Goal-Focused Leader Behavior with the Mediating Role of the Bottom-Line Mentality of Leaders - **Authors:** Muhammad Azeem Ahmad - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of social sciences review - **Publication Date:** 2023-03-31 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.54183/jssr.v3i1.273

366. Establishing a Dignity Scale - Measuring Intrinsic Value within Social Contexts - **Authors:** Michael Pirson, Ralph L. Piedmont, Noemi Nagy et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Humanistic management journal - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s41463-023-00147-7

369. Ethical Culture in Organizations: A Review and Agenda for Future Research - **Authors:** Achinto Roy, Alexander Newman, Heather Round et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Business Ethics Quarterly - **Publication Date:** 2023-04-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1017/beq.2022.44

373. Ethical leadership and workplace behavior in the education sector: The implications of employees' ethical work behavior - **Authors:** Fengrui Guo, Zhong Xue, Jiaxun He et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Frontiers in Psychology - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-04 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1040000

376. The Psychological Outcomes for Leadership and Employees in the Education Sector - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** Frontiers research topics - **Publication Date:** 2023-01-01 - **Type:** Book - **DOI:** 10.3389/978-2-8325-4120-3

377. How bottom-line mentality leads to Abusive Supervision? Investigating the Mediating effects of anxiety - **Authors:** Xuan Zheng, Ling Zhang - **Journal/Venue:** Psychology Research and Behavior Management - **Publication Date:** 2023-11-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.2147/prbm.s436568

396. Cross-country comparative trend analysis in ESG regulatory framework across developed and developing nations - **Authors:** Monica Singhanian, Neha Saini, C. Shri et al. - **Journal/Venue:** Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal - **Publication Date:** 2023-08-29 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/meq-02-2023-0056

425. Corporate social responsibility (CSR): The role of government in promoting CSR - **Authors:** Douglas D. Thomas - **Journal/Venue:** Journal of The Knowledge Economy - **Publication Date:** 2023-05-23 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1007/s13132-023-01185-0

2022 (49 papers)

19. Dodging the bullet: overcoming the financial impact of Ukraine armed conflict with sustainable business strategies and environmental approaches - **Authors:** Marina Mattera, Federico Soto - **Journal/Venue:** The Journal of Risk Finance - **Publication Date:** 2022-12-05 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.1108/jrf-04-2022-0092

41. The Palgrave handbook of ESG and corporate governance - **Authors:** P Câmara, F Morais - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2022-01-01 - **Type:** Book - **DOI:** 10.1007/978-3-030-99468-6

44. Raising Environmental and Social Sustainability through Green Human Resources Practices in Egyptian Tourism & Hospitality Organisations; the Mediating Role of Pro-Environmental Behaviors - **Authors:** N. A. Morsy, Hesham Dar - **Journal/Venue:** Mağallaṯ Kulliyyaṯ al-siāḥaṯ wa al-fanādiq (Ĝāmi'at al-Mansoura) - **Publication Date:** 2022-06-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.21608/mkaf.2022.254017

45. Naya, Patricia Tiimah; (2022) Developing tools and evidence to deliver prosperity. The era of inclusivity: employees driving green human resource management toward sustainable prosperity - **Authors:** No authors - **Journal/Venue:** No venue - **Publication Date:** 2022-08-01 - **Type:** Journal Article - **DOI:** 10.14324/000.wp.10153088

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